

PREVENTION OF VIOLENCE, EXPLOITATION, CRUELTY AND DISCRIMINATION AGAINST CHILDREN

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Bobonazarova Gozalkhon

4th grade student in the field of preschool education at Urganch State University

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Comprehensive measures for the prevention of crimes in our country, in particular, raising the legal consciousness and culture of the population, being kind to children, and improving the cooperation of state organizations and other institutions of civil society in this regard, in order to expand the scope of work in this field in the activities of self-governing organization a number of reforms are being implemented.

Key words

protection of children, tendency, doughy environment, convention, violence, exploitation, antisocial behavior.

Scientific and practical studies show that the reasons for committing crimes, the formation of antisocial behavior and characteristics in a person, and the commission of various types of offenses, the law or law enforcement, and the factors that hinder its observance are caused by the influence of the family atmosphere. Because, an doughy socio-psychological atmosphere in the family plays an important role in the origin of any crime. It is known that the basics of any offense and negative vices are formed in the family. The family is important in the formation of human characteristics such as preparing a person for social life, spiritual and moral education, behavior in the process of social relations with individuals.

Effective measures of regulatory legal documents have been developed for the perfect development of children, the practical expression of their legal rights and interests, and the prevention of violence and various pressures on children. In particular, the main directions of the state policy on the protection of children's rights are defined, which are as follows:

- ensuring the rights, freedoms and legal interests of the child;
- protection of the child's life and health;
- not to allow the child to be discriminated against;
- protection of the honor and dignity of the child;

- ensuring equal rights and opportunities for children;
- improvement of the legal basis of guarantees of children's rights.

In addition, with the adoption of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to further strengthen the guarantees of children's rights" dated April 22, 2019 PD-4296, the Ombudsman now has a deputy, that is, a representative for children's rights.

The Convention on the Rights of the Child was adopted in New York on November 20, 1989 and entered into force on September 2, 1990. Today, the number of member states of the Convention is 196. It is interesting that the number of countries that signed the convention, but did not ratify it, is 1 (USA).

According to the convention, the child is considered as an independent person. The Convention describes the child as a person with specific rights: the right to live (Article 6), to found a family (Article 9), to name and nationality.

On education (Article 7), on protection from violence (Article 19), on equality, freedom of thought and expression (Article 13), rest and recreation (Article 31), medical services and health care (Article 24), state assistance (Articles 18-27), etc.

Violence is an attack on another person's life, health, sexual integrity, honor, dignity and other rights and freedoms protected by law by intentionally exerting physical, mental, sexual or economic influence on another person or threatening to use measures of such influence is an illegal action (inaction).

In domestic violence, it is understood that the act (inaction) of violence is committed against other members of the family (wife, parents, children, etc.). In general, according to statistical data, women and children suffer from domestic violence in most cases. Domestic violence can take the form of sexual, physical, economic and psychological violence.

In our constitution, a number of basic rights and obligations of citizens, in particular, that no one can be subjected to torture, violence, cruel or other forms of oppression degrading human dignity, equal rights of women and men, citizens are obliged to comply with the Constitution and laws, to respect the rights, freedoms, honor and dignity of other people, and everyone must comply with these requirements.

As international awareness of the serious social and economic harm caused by violence against children grows, the protection of children from violence, exploitation, abuse and discrimination is becoming a significant task in the world. In Uzbekistan, the components of the child protection system exist at the institutional level, and the protection of children is regulated by a complex legal

framework. National priorities for reforming the family and child protection system, as well as the judicial system, are outlined in the national strategy.

The ability of parents to meet children's needs and influence children's behavior is a direct factor influencing modern tendency in child protection. Permanent or sudden weakening of the family, such as poverty, death of a father or mother, migration or separation of parents, absence or loss of housing, and the inability of the family to solve the listed problems, leading to children's "antisocial behavior", child trafficking or neglect can make you weak. Parents' inability to communicate positively with children, how to deal with children's hyper-responsibility and difficult behavior, and their lack of understanding of behavioral changes during adolescence also increase children's risk of maltreatment and violence, and can lead to the permanent breakdown of family relationships causes possible family conflicts. In addition, alcohol and drug abuse also increase the risk of direct harm to children. Although the issue of domestic and gender violence is not widely discussed in the society, such events are also observed in Uzbekistan.

Political, regulatory and institutional frameworks, child protection legislation reforms have recently been implemented and the legal framework for child protection needs to be strengthened, despite a significant expansion. The concept of "the best benefits of the child", the type of violence, and the legal basis for providing services to children who are victims of violence should be further defined in the legislation. In addition, the complexity of child protection cases requires a cross-sectoral approach conditioned by the need to have sufficient capacity and to ensure coherence between sectors such as social services, internal affairs, the justice system, health and education.

Different organizations operating in the field of child protection in Uzbekistan often have overlapping functions, coordination and integration between them is required, and the child protection system is fragmented. Capacity for planning, monitoring and regular evaluation of child protection programs and results should be strengthened at the national level in relevant ministries.

REFERENCE:

- 1 Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 7, 2008 "On Guarantees of Children's Rights" No. ORQ-139;
- 2 Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. PQ-4296 dated 22.04.2019;
- 3 Analysis of the situation of children in Uzbekistan; UNICEF 2020.